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Television advertisements: Creating awareness or problems to the television viewers

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Abstract

Television advertisements reach larger, more captive audiences in short time. They attract attention and awareness well and provide general messages about the products or services. There are a number of advantages of television advertising; yet there are some drawbacks too. Several criticisms and objections are put forth against Television advertisements. In order to make the television advertisements effective, the problems arise by the Television advertisements should be removed. This study aims to find whether the television advertisements are creating problems to the television viewers or awareness about the products or services. This study is an empirical research. Findings of this study reveal are the major problem arises due to television advertisements is that they exaggerate the features of the product, the most of the television viewers are having high degree of awareness about the products which are advertised in television and the most of the television viewers feel that the quality of the product cannot be ascertained through television advertisements.

Keywords: advertisement copy, awareness, media, television advertisement, television viewers.

1. Introduction

In the present world of advertising, different types of media are being used, of which, television is the most popular one. Television advertising has taken the role of personal selling to a large extent. Television provides a scientific synchronization of features of sound, sight, motion and immediacy. So television advertisement has important advantages over newspapers, magazines and radio as the media of advertising. Television advertising remains a very effective method to reach potential clients and customers. Television advertising offers the benefit of reaching large numbers in a single exposure. Yet television lacks the ability to deliver an advertisement to highly targeted customers compared to other media outlets.¹ The goal of television commercials is to inform their target audience of what the advertiser has to offer as well as to persuade them to consider purchasing the product or service being offered.

1. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Recall is one of the key measures used in advertising effectiveness testing, along with others such as persuasion and advertising liking. It has been known for long that advertising must arouse some emotion to be effective: Triggering meaningful emotional responses is key in branding as consumers decision-making processes around brands have a heavy emotion-based dimension to them.²

Advertising creates social identification and cohesion and offers a shared symbolic language for communication in different contexts.³

A common way to measure advertising awareness is to ask people if they remember seeing the advertisement for a specific brand. This form of advertising awareness remains one of the core metrics used in advertising tracking because it can generate a) top-of-mind, b) total unprompted and c) prompted advertising awareness. Those three measures are used to assess overall advertising effectiveness.⁴

Television's effectiveness is stable or even increasing because marketers are getting better at deciding when to use television in light of a growing number of media available. Overall, the continued effectiveness of television advertising depends on its adaptability to new trends, such as interactive television.⁵

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2. Methodology

This study is an empirical research. The primary data were collected directly from the sample respondents by interviewing them personally by using interview schedule. Survey method is adopted for this study.

3. Sampling Design

The sample respondent should be the representative of the population. In such a way the hundred and twenty sample respondents were selected in Erode District, Tamilnadu by using non-probability convenience sampling method during the period October 2014. From each educational status namely illiterates, school level and college level an equal number of sample respondents were selected.

4. Framework of Analysis

The data collected were transcribed in long sheets and from them tables were prepared and analyzed with the help of the available techniques such as 'Percentage' and 'Weighted Average Method'.

5. Problems Arise Due To Television Advertisements

Though there are number of advantages in television advertisement several criticisms are put forth against it. In order to make the television advertisements effective, the problems arising due to television advertisements are to be removed. The problems created by television advertisements are analyzed in this study. There are ten problems were considered for analysis. They are 'Awkward advertisements', 'Disturbance', 'Confusing in selecting the best product', 'Not Understandable', 'Do not convey more about product', 'Exaggeration', 'Annoyed by advertisements', 'Wasting the time', 'Force to buy unnecessary things' and 'Increasing the cost of the product'.

Awkward Advertisements

Television advertisements contain outraging sentiments, exciting emotions, vulgar statements, nude poses of fair sex and all these are given undue value. Some of them are full of sex appeal, cupidity, vulgar, silly and stupid in that they appeal to shame, fear and envy. These are offensive to public decency, affect the morale of the younger generation and damage the ethical aims of a society.

Disturbance

The television advertisements disturb the television viewers when they watching the programmes in television. So they may get irritation due to disturbance.

Confusing in Selecting the Best Product

Many products are advertised in television those are having similar features. Every advertisement in television shows its product as the best. So the television viewers may get confusion in selecting the best product to purchase.

Not Understandable

Some advertisements are not understandable immediately. Television viewers that just see once may not understand the information given in advertisement. So they are not convinced by the advertisement. Hence the advertiser has to repeat the advertisement and increase the frequency. Repeat Advertisements in television is expensive.

Do Not Convey More about Product

Television advertisements are mostly too short. So it may not convey more information about the products. The information given by the television advertisements are very limited and insufficient to take purchase decision.

Exaggeration

Television advertisements exaggerate the real fact to the consumers. Most of the producers advertise their products not with a view to serve the public, but with a view to dispose of their products, which are really not needed to the customers. They aim at earning profits by pushing out the dead stocks. For this, by concealing the actual facts, the advertiser makes publicity with 'make to believe' statements by using false statistics, tempered statements, false claims, exaggerated ideas, false comparison, misrepresented opinions of great people and false supported reports without a base. It leads the consumer to buy that product even though it is low quality or may be ineffective.

Annoyed by Advertisements

Most of the television viewers avoid television advertisements. They feel that there is no use of advertisements. So they are annoyed by the advertisements. It tends to change channel during advertisements time or go to do some other work.

Wasting the Time

The programme time is lengthened due to the intervention of the advertisements. So the television viewers are in a position to spend large time to watch a programme. Because of this the time of the television viewers become waste.

Force to Buy Unnecessary Things

People are forced to buy unnecessary things by the attraction of the television advertisements. It also induces the people to buy harmful product such as cigarettes, brandy etc. which will affect their health. Thus it stimulates people to go in for things, which they cannot afford but it multiplies the needs.

Increasing the Cost of the Product

Television advertisements have to depend on the creativeness. If the advertisements are not creative enough, television viewers will not pay attention and the product will not sell off. If advertising fails to sell the product, then the price will be increased. The television advertisements increase the price of the product since manufacturers spend a lot of money on television advertisements. In a virtual sense, it is an unproductive expenditure, which increases the prices and the ultimate sufferers are the consumers.

Table 1: Problems Faced By the Television Viewers: Ranking Analysis

S. No	Problems	Rank 1		Rank 2		Rank 3		Rank 4		Rank 5		Rank 6		Rank 7		Rank 8		Rank 9		Rank 10		Total Score
		No. of respondents	Score																			
1	Awkward advertisements	17	170	10	90	11	88	7	49	15	90	9	45	12	48	9	27	12	24	18	18	649
2	Disturbance	13	130	8	72	15	120	10	70	11	66	11	55	14	56	16	48	14	28	8	8	653
3	Confusing in selecting the best product	5	50	18	162	13	104	11	77	14	84	14	70	10	40	14	42	14	28	7	7	664
4	Not Understandable	8	80	12	108	12	96	19	133	9	54	16	80	13	52	12	36	11	22	8	8	669
5	Do not convey more about product	17	170	12	108	9	72	13	91	14	84	10	50	11	44	7	21	10	20	17	17	677
6	Exaggeration	15	150	18	162	10	80	10	70	12	72	9	45	8	32	11	33	11	22	16	16	682
7	Annoyed by advertisements	13	130	12	108	14	112	8	56	12	72	12	60	10	40	15	45	14	28	10	10	661
8	Wasting the time	14	140	4	36	14	112	9	63	11	66	13	65	18	72	12	36	13	26	12	12	628
9	Force to buy unnecessary things	9	90	9	81	13	104	20	140	12	72	15	75	9	36	10	30	12	24	11	11	663
10	Increasing the cost of the product	9	90	17	153	9	72	13	91	10	60	11	55	15	60	14	42	9	18	13	13	654
Total		120		120		120		120		120		120		120		120		120		120		

In order to find the degree in which the problems affect the television viewers, the respondents are asked to assign the rank for the problems. After that by using weighted average technique the score was given to each and every problem. Finally the problem, which scores the more points, got the first rank. Then the problem, which scores next to the high score, got the second rank. Like these the problems are assigned by the rank. The points scored by each and every problem faced by the television viewers are shown in Table I. The rank was assigned according to its total scores and the result is given in Table II.

Table 2: Problems Due To Television Advertisements According To Its Rank

S.No	Problems due to Television Advertisements	Rank	Total Score
1	Exaggeration	1	682
2	Do not convey more about product	2	677
3	Not Understandable	3	669
4	Confusing in selecting the best product	4	664
5	Force to buy unnecessary things	5	663
6	Annoyed by advertisements	6	661
7	Increasing the cost of the product	7	654
8	Disturbance	8	653
9	Awkward advertisements	9	649
10	Wasting the time	10	628

It can be seen from Table II that the television viewers are mostly suffered by the television advertisements which are

exaggerate the products by concealing the reality. After that the television advertisements are not providing sufficient information about the products. Sometimes the advertisements are not in understandable manner. It also confuses the viewers to select the best product to purchase. The television advertisements force the television viewers to buy unnecessary things. The television viewers are getting angry and irritated by the advertisements. If the television advertisement increase the sales then the large scale production is possible. It leads to reduction in price. Otherwise the cost of the product will be increased by the television advertisements. Most of the times the television viewers are treat the television advertisements as disturbance. The awkward advertisements are damage the ethical aims of the society. Above all the television advertisements waste the time of the television viewers. These are all the problems arising due to television advertisements.

6. Awareness Created By Television Advertisements

The present era is of mass production and mass distribution. Similar products are taken to the market. There are many substitutes in the market. So the public must know the best product. As a mass communication media television advertisements have the responsibility to the television viewers in creating awareness about the product. In order to find the effectiveness of television advertisements in creating awareness about consumer product, this study focuses on the awareness of television viewers about consumer products which are advertised in television.

TABLE 3: Awareness Created By Television Advertisements

S.No	Statements	Agree		Disagree		Total no. of respondents
		No. of respondents	Percentage	No. of respondents	Percentage	
1	Help to know about the availability of new products	101	84.17	19	15.83	120
2	Quality of the products can be ascertained	52	43.33	68	56.67	120
3	Method of handling of the product can be known	67	55.83	53	44.17	120
4	Help to know about the usage of the product	108	90.00	12	10.00	120
5	Precaution activities to be taken when handling the product are made known	86	71.67	34	28.33	120
6	Help to know about the place of availability	94	78.33	26	21.67	120
7	The cost of the product can be made known	65	54.17	55	45.83	120
8	Best product can be found by making comparison with rival product	58	48.33	62	51.67	120
9	Features of the product can be made known	79	65.83	41	34.17	120
10	Increase the knowledge about the product	91	75.83	29	24.17	120

The television advertisements have important place in introducing the new products. It provides the information relating to the products. Through television advertisements, the television viewers can get awareness about the products. But the degree of awareness created by television advertisements will differ from person to person. Some people have ability to perceive anything quickly. Another some people may not have that ability. The television advertisements should be accordance with those people. In order to find the efficiency of television advertisements in creating awareness about consumer product ten statements have been given to the respondents. These statements are prepared in the manner in which the television advertisements are creating the awareness about the product. From the Table III it can be known that the most of the respondents (108) agree that 'the television advertisements help to know about the usage of the product'. The least of the respondents (52) agree that 'the quality of the products can be ascertained'.

To find the score value, Likert's 2-point scale system (agree, disagree) has been applied. Based on these score the respondents are classified into two. That is the television viewers who are having high degree of awareness about advertised product and having less degree of awareness about advertised product. The result obtained from this analysis is given in Table IV.

Table 4: Awareness of Television Viewers about Advertised Products

Awareness	No. of respondents	Percentage
Highly Aware	93	77.50
Less Aware	27	22.50
Total	120	100.00

It can be found from the Table 4 that out of 120 sample respondents 93 respondents (77.50%) were having high degree of awareness about advertised product and 27 sample

respondents (22.50%) were having less degree of awareness about advertised product.

7. Major Findings And Suggestions

From this study it is found that the three problems, which are highly, affect the people by the television advertisements are (a) they exaggerate the products by concealing the real facts (b) they do not convey all the information about the product and (c) some information given by the television advertisements are not understandable. It is suggested that the advertiser has to highly concentrate on these three problems while preparing the advertisement copy for effective advertisement.

Only the least of the respondents are agreed that by watching the television advertisements (a) the quality of the advertised products can be easily ascertained (b) best products can be found by making comparison with rival product and (c) the cost of the products can be made known. To improve the quality of television advertisements all the information about the advertised products such as the quality and cost of the product must be clearly made known to the public and it should be in such a way that it helps to compare with its rival products.

The study also shows that 77.50% of the sample respondents have high awareness about the products which are advertised in television. They feel that the television advertisements introduce the new products, educate the features of the product, help to increase the knowledge about the product and help to select best product for making purchase. The remaining 22.50% of the sample respondents have less awareness about the products which are advertised in television. According to them the television advertisements are not providing sufficient information about the products and most of these are not in understandable manner. While preparing the advertisement copy the advertiser has to make sure that the all information about the product were clearly given in the advertisement.

8. Conclusion

Television is a common traditional medium used by companies to promote their brand and products. Television gives a lot of creative opportunities, access to a large audience in many cases, and multi-sensory appeal. So the television advertisements are having the prominent place in the marketing. They may have both positive and negative attributes. The quality of the television advertisements can be improved by removing the negative attributes. The manufacturers, advertisers and the government are having the responsibility to improve the quality of television advertisements. There is no doubt that the quality of the television advertisements will be improved by implementing these suggestions.

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